

GROWTH IN AREA AND PRODUCTION OF SERICULTURE IN NORTH-EASTERN STATES-A SPECIAL REFERENCE TO ASSAM

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Abstract

The sericulture industry provides sustainable income for the rural people and generates higher income; and provides employment to both skilled and unskilled labor (Lakshman *et al.*, 1998). The North Eastern India contributes about 99 per cent of total production of Muga in the country and designated as world monopoly for the golden yellow muga silk. However, there is a lot demand for the non-mulberry silk outside the India. This study aims to examine the share of various North Eastern states in area and production of sericulture, district-wise share in Assam using secondary data relating to area and production of cocoon and raw silk like Eri, Muga and Mulberry for the period from 2001-02 to 2015-16. The share of North-eastern states in India's total area under mulberry and total raw silk production was increased significantly during the study period. Assam and Manipur were the leading states contributing to the increase in area under mulberry and raw silk production of North-Eastern states. The growth rate of area under Eri and Muga silk were 1.96 percent and 1.64 percent respectively but found negative for Mulberry silk (-0.43%) for state as a whole. In most of the districts of Assam, growth rates were positive and significant for area under Eri and Muga. Growth in raw silk production was higher in Eri (14.77%) followed by Mulberry (7.81%) and Muga (2.59%) in the state.

Keywords: Sericulture, area, production, percentage share, growth rate.

Introduction:

The sericulture provides income and employment all round the year and fetches higher income to the rural farm families. Sericulture has been an important income generating cottage-based industry in the country. The industry has been providing sustainable income for different strata of people in the rural society including the landless (Manjunatha *et al.* 2015) and generates higher income; and provides employment to both skilled and unskilled labor (Lakshman *et al.* 1998).

Sericulture refers to the conscious mass-scale rearing of silk producing organisms to obtain silk. It involves cultivation of food plants, production of silkworm eggs, rearing of silkworm by feeding them the leaves of the food plants to obtain cocoon and yarn from the cocoon by reeling or spinning. There are four major varieties of silk namely, Mulberry, Eri, Muga and Tasar, each of which is produced by a distinct variety of silkworm feeding on a specific host plant. It is practiced in a wide range of agro-climatic regions like forests, hilly areas and plains. In fact, the recent technological advancements have made it possible to practice it on an intensive scale, mainly due to increased profits obtained from it as compared to most of the crops and enterprises. Sericulture is also known as "Industry of the Poor", the end product of which is silk, "the queen of fabrics".

India is emerging as a major silk producing country in the world. India is the second largest producer and consumer of silk and its allied products after China. In the global textile parlance, the term 'silk' refers to the silk of mulberry origin, as almost 95 per cent of the world total silk production consists of mulberry silk (Ullal and Narasimhannan, 1994).

In India, sericulture can be found in different regions i.e. temperate (Kashmir), subtropical (Jammu, Himachal Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh, N.E Region) and tropical (West Bengal, Bihar, Orissa, Madhya Pradesh, Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu and Karnataka). Among them, Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal are noted for Mulberry silk and Assam and other North Eastern states are famous for non- mulberry silk or Vanya silk. India has sericulture tradition and has the unique peculiarity of having all the four commercially viable varieties of silk viz., Mulberry, Tasar, Eri and Muga (Kumar 2008).

Mulberry silk, produced extensively in the state of Karnataka, West Bengal and Jammu and Kashmir. About 80 per cent of the country's production is contributed by Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh and West Bengal. Other states namely, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh and

Maharashtra contribute about 11 per cent to total production of mulberry silk in India (Lakshman 2007).

Tasar silk, Jharkhand is the leading producer of silk followed by Chhattisgarh, Orissa and Madhya Pradesh. Eri silk which is also called as "Endisilk", practiced extensively in North Eastern states. Assam stood first in production of Eri silk followed by Meghalaya and Nagaland. Muga silk, is also called as 'Golden silk'. The North Eastern India alone contributes 99 per cent of total production of Muga in the country. India enjoys the world monopoly for the golden yellow muga silk. In the backdrop of this the study was examined the percentage share and growth rate of sericulture in North Eastern states and all districts of Assam.

Methodology:

The present study was conducted in North Eastern states; Assam and its major sericulture districts (Karbi – Anglong, N.C. Hills, Lakhimpur, Sivasagar, Golaghat, Dhemaji and Dibrugarh). North East India comprises eight states viz., Assam, Arunachal Pradesh, Manipur, Mizoram, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Sikkim, and Tripura. The study was entirely based on secondary data relating to area and production of cocoon and raw silk of Eri, Muga and Mulberry for the period from 2001-02 to 2015-16 collected for all the districts of Assam and North eastern states from different published sources such as Statistical Handbook of Assam, Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Guwahati and Annual Reports of Central Silk Board (CSB), Bangalore. To know the percentage share and district wise distribution of cocoon and raw silk, tabular analysis with averages and percentages were used for examining the area and production in the study area.

Compound Growth Rate (CGR) analysis

In the present study, district wise growth in area, cocoon production and production of silk were analyzed using the exponential growth rate function. The Compound Growth Rates (CGR) for area, production of different types of silk varieties *i.e.*, Eri, Muga and Mulberry grown in the selected districts of Assam were estimated for the period from 2001-02 to 2015-16. The semi log exponential functional form was used to analyze the trend in growth rate, which is one of the appropriate functional forms to estimate the growth rate.

$$Y = a b^t e$$

Where,

Y= Dependent variable for which growth rate is estimated

a = Intercept

b = Regression coefficient

t = Time variable

e = Error term

Since the model being the multiplicative the function was transformed into additive model by simple logarithmic transformation as below:

$$\ln Y = \ln a + t \ln b$$

The per cent compound growth rate (CAGR) was derived using following formulae

$$\text{CAGR} = (\text{Anti ln of } b - 1) \times 100$$

Growth rate is indicated by the value and sign of the 'b' coefficient. If coefficient is statistically significant and positive then growth of the estimated parameters over the years is positive or accelerating. If the value of 'b' coefficient is negative, it indicates that growth is negative or decelerating during the reference period.

Results and Discussion:

Share of North Eastern states in area under mulberry

Table 1 shows the share of different states in total area under mulberry cultivation in North East India. The total area under mulberry was 14785 hectares accounting for 6.37 per cent of India's area under mulberry (232076 hectares) in 2001-02 which increased to 26398 hectares registering a sharp raise of 12.63 per cent of India's area under mulberry (208946 hectares) in 2015-16. Among the North Eastern states, contribution to total area of North East India under mulberry was found to increase for states like Assam, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Sikkim and Tripura. However, share of Arunachal Pradesh, Manipur and Nagaland declined during the period from 2001-02 to 2015-16. Manipur had the highest share (48.11%) in 2001-02 among all the North Eastern states but it decreased to 27.80 per cent in 2015-16 due to shifting cultivation in hilly areas. Share of Assam was increased from 26.16 per cent in 2001-02 to 30.12 per cent in 2010-11 and then marginally reduced to 29.42 per cent in 2015-16.

Share of North Eastern states in total silk production

Table 2 shows the share of different states in total silk production of North East India. The total silk production in North East India was 1318 MT accounting for 7.60 per cent of India's total silk production (17350.5 MT) in 2001-02 which increased to 5487.97 MT registering a share of 12.63 per cent of India's total silk production (28523 MT) in 2015-16. Contribution of all the states to total silk production of North East India was found to increase barring Manipur and Meghalaya. Assam accounted for the highest share in total silk production in North East India. Its contribution was increased from 42.03 per cent to 60.59 per cent for the study period.

District wise share in area and production of sericulture in Assam

The share of the selected districts in state's total area, cocoon production and raw silk production under different types silk are presented in this section.

Share of different districts of Assam in area under sericulture

Table 3 reveals the share of total area (in hectares) under sericulture for the selected districts of Assam from 2001-02 to 2015-16. It is observed that all selected districts were prominent share in terms of area under sericulture from 2001-02 to 2010-11 however, declined during 2015-16 due to farmers switching over to other crops like paddy, tea etc. except in case of Dhemaji and Dibrugarh districts. which increased from 5.73 percent in 2001-02 to 13.23 percent in 2015-16. The share of other districts of Assam were increased from 60.31 to 68.64 percent for the selected study period. The share of Dhemaji and Dibrugarh increased from 5.73 and 4.61 per cent in 2001-02 to 13.23 and 5.75 per cent respectively in 2015-16. The share of other districts also increased from 60.31 percent to 68.64 percent during the study period.

Share of different districts of Assam in cocoon production

Table 4 shows the district wise share of total cocoon production (in MT) of Eri, Muga and Mulberry in the state from 2001-02 to 2015-16. An analysis of cocoon production in the districts revealed that barring Sivasagar total cocoon production declined during the study period 2001-02 to 2015-16. The share of Sivasagar was increased from 11.63 percent to 12.11 percent. The shares of Karbi Anglong,

N.C. Hills, Lakhimpur, Goalaghat, Dhemaji and Dibrugarh in the state's total cocoon production were 5.03, 1.89, 16.64, 5.56, 8.36 and 14.37 per cent respectively in 2001-02 which declined to 3.53, 0.69, 6.98, 3.24, 7.63 and 6.41 per cent respectively in 2015-16. However, the share of other districts were increased from 36.53 percent to 59.40 percent. The reasons for declining share of the majority of the districts in state's total cocoon production might be due to climatic variation, improper management of plantation, decline in production of muga cocoon as muga cocoons are produced in the tree itself and get affected by temperature variation.

Share of different districts of Assam in total silk production

Table 5 shows district wise share in the total silk production (in MT) of eri, muga, mulberry for the period 2001-02 to 2015-16 in Assam. Among the districts Sivasagar, increased share in raw silk production was 5.76 to 8.47 per cent however, for Karbi-Anglong (19.83 to 4.39%), N.C. Hills (7.15 to 0.56%), Lakhimpur (6.93 to 1.92%), Goalaghat (5.49 to 1.78%), Dhemaji (5.42% to 3.36%) and Dibrugarh (5.36 to 3.77 %) was found to be declined during the study period. In most of the districts silk production declined mainly due to post cocoon problems or quality problems in cocoons.

Growth rate of area and production of cocoon and silk of Eri, Muga and Mulberry

It is evident from Table 6, that the growth of area under eri (1.96%) in Assam was slightly higher than the growth of area under muga (1.64%) during the period from 2001-02 to 2015-16. On the other hand, area under mulberry declined at an annual growth rate of -0.43 per cent during the same period. Among the districts, growth in area under eri was found to be positive and statically significant for Dhemaji (6.24%) and Dibrugarh (4.94%). Growth rate of area under muga was found to be positive and significant for Karbi Anglong (4.34%), N.C. Hills (10.35%), and Dhemaji (3.27%). As regards to growth of area under mulberry, negative growth was observed for most of the selected districts of Assam. Decrease in area under mulberry in most of the districts of Assam might be due to expansion of tea gardens to the eri and muga plantations, lack of interest of the farmers for mulberry cultivation because of its low demand etc.

From the table 6 it is noticed that cocoon production of eri silk was increased at an compound annual growth rate of 14.50 per cent for the state as a whole during the period from 2001-02 to 2015-16. The growth rates were positive and statistically significant for Lakhimpur (13.79 %), Goalaghat (17.97 %) and Dhemaji (9.73 %). Growth rate of cocoon production of muga silk for the state as whole was found to be 3.06 per cent during the study period. Among the selected districts, the growth rate was statistically significant only in Dhemaji (3.54 %). Mulberry cocoon production in Assam was found to increase at an annual compound growth rate of 10.03 per cent during the period from 2001-02 to 2015-16. All the district of Assam showed positive growth in mulberry cocoon production during the same period.

Raw silk production of eri silk in Assam registered a CAGR of 14.77 per cent during the study period. From the Table 6 it is observed that all the districts showed positive growth rate for raw silk production, The growth rates were found to be statistically significant for Golaghat (17.83%), Dibrugarh (15.40%), Jorhat (15.32%), Lakhimpur (14.12%), and Dhemaji (10.30%) districts respectively. In case of muga raw silk production, a positive and significant growth rate of 2.59 per cent was observed for the state of Assam. District-wise analysis revealed that all the districts had a positive growth rate with the exception of Lakhimpur district with CGR of - 5.04 per cent but significant. Raw silk production of mulberry silk in Assam registered a significant and positive CAGR of 7.81 per cent during the study period. From the Table 6 it is observed that all the districts showed positive growth rate for mulberry raw silk production. The growth rates were found to be statistically significant for Dhemaji (12.90%) and Lakhimpur (9.08%) districts respectively.

From the above analysis, it was observed that raw silk production of Eri, muga and mulberry was increased in the state as well as majority

of the districts of Assam during the period from 2001-02 to 2015-16. The reason for this increase in raw silk production of all the category of silk might be attributed to the factors like (i) adoption of new input technology, (ii) new hybrid silk worms of eri and muga introduced by

Central Eri and Muga Research and Training Institute, Jorhat for high yield and quality of cocoons, (iii) advanced methods in reeling for raw silk production.

Table 01: State wise percentage share of area (ha) under Mulberry in North East India (2001-02 to 2015-16)

State	2001-02	2005-06	2010-11	2015-16
Assam	3921 (26.16)	4518 (27.34)	6824 (31.03)	7765 (29.42)
Arunachal Pradesh	211 (1.43)	246 (1.49)	210(0.95)	341(1.29)
Manipur	7113 (48.11)	5513(33.36)	6175(28.08)	7338(27.80)
Mizoram	990 (6.70)	4061(24.57)	5280(24.01)	3843(14.56)
Meghalaya	948 (6.41)	1014(6.14)	1298 (5.90)	3009(11.40)
Nagaland	763 (5.16)	370(2.24)	424(1.93)	743(2.81)
Sikkim	86 (0.58)	0.00(0.00)	189(0.86)	198(0.75)
Tripura	806 (5.45)	806(4.88)	1590(7.23)	3161(11.97)
North East India	14785 (100.00)	16528(100.00)	21990(100.00)	26398(100.00)
Share of North East India to India	232076 (6.37)	179065.28(9.23)	170314(12.91)	208946.7 (12.63)

Note: Figures in the parentheses indicate percentage share

Table 02: State wise percentage share of total silk production (MT) in Eri, Muga, and Mulberry in North East India (2001-02 -2015-16)

State	2001-02	2005-06	2010-11	2015-16
Assam	554 (42.03)	857 (54.12)	1749 (60.08)	3325 (60.59)
Arunachal Pradesh	3.50 (0.27)	11.24 (0.71)	20.2 (0.69)	37 (0.67)
Manipur	424.50 (32.21)	283.06 (17.88)	319.5 (10.97)	515 (9.38)
Mizoram	7 (0.53)	9.07 (0.57)	32.9 (1.13)	64.12 (1.17)
Meghalaya	289 (21.93)	288 (18.19)	492.25 (16.91)	857 (15.62)
Nagaland	36 (2.73)	131.18 (8.28)	284.4 (9.77)	631 (11.50)
Sikkim	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	5 (0.17)	6.85 (0.12)
Tripura	4 (0.30)	4 (0.25)	8 (0.27)	52 (0.95)
North East India	1318 (100.00)	1583.55 (100.00)	2911.25 (100.00)	5487.97 (100.00)
Share of North East India to India	17350.5 (7.60)	191893 (0.83)	20409.8 (14.26)	28523 (19.24)

Note: Figures in the parentheses indicate percentage share

Table 3: District wise percentage share of total area (ha) under Eri, Muga, Mulberry in Assam for the period 2001-02 to 2015-16

District	2000-01	2005-06	2010-11	2015-16
Karbi-Anglong	895 (6.12)	1062 (5.72)	1091.5 (5.12)	292.65 (2.56)
N.C.Hills	408 (2.79)	421 (2.27)	590.5 (2.77)	208.71 (1.83)
Lakhimpur	1548 (10.59)	1727(9.31)	2032.46 (9.54)	462.86 (4.05)
Sivasagar	928 (6.35)	1187 (6.40)	1324.25 (6.22)	332.27 (2.91)
Goalaghat	513 (3.51)	670 (3.61)	1099.59 (5.16)	118.21 (1.03)
Dhemaji	838 (5.73)	1530 (8.25)	1375.5 (6.46)	1512.81 (13.23)
Dibrugarh	674 (4.61)	855 (4.61)	1053.3 (4.94)	657.95 (5.75)
Others	8818 (60.31)	11104 (59.84)	12734.1 (59.78)	7848.83 (68.64)
Assam	14622 (100)	18556 (100.00)	21301.17 (100.00)	11434.29(100.00)

Table 4: District wise percentage share of total cocoon production (MT) of Eri, Muga, Mulberry in Assam (2001-02 to 2015-16)

District	2000-01	2005-06	2010-11	2015-16
Karbi-Anglong	138.57 (5.03)	85.81 (2.86)	221.7 (5.48)	191.62 (3.53)
N.C.Hills	52.03 (1.89)	20.07 (0.67)	50.06 (1.24)	37.61 (0.69)
Lakhimpur	458.1 (16.64)	788.22 (26.28)	566.32 (13.99)	379.02 (6.98)
Sivasagar	320.2 (11.63)	333.04 (11.10)	430.17 (10.63)	657.66 (12.11)
Goalaghat	153.06 (5.56)	154.58 (5.15)	373.85 (9.23)	176.11 (3.24)
Dhemaji	230.14 (8.36)	221.09 (7.37)	365.22 (9.02)	414.39 (7.63)
Dibrugarh	395.57 (14.37)	94.53 (3.15)	238.96 (5.90)	348.11 (6.41)
Others	1005.95 (36.53)	1302.07 (43.41)	1802 (44.51)	3225.48 (59.40)
Assam	2753.62 (100.00)	2999.41(100.00)	4048.28 (100.00)	5430 (100.00)

Table 5: District wise percentage share of total raw silk production (MT) in Eri, Muga, Mulberry in Assam (2001-02 to 2015-16)

District	2000-01	2005-06	2010-11	2015-16
Karbi-Anglong	106.64 (19.83)	62.48 (9.83)	174.26 (18.63)	119.12 (4.39)
N.C.Hills	38.47 (7.15)	14.84 (2.34)	37.1 (3.97)	15.11 (0.56)
Lakhimpur	37.26 (6.93)	51.88 (8.17)	54.27 (5.80)	52.02 (1.92)
Sivasagar	31 (5.76)	40.72 (6.41)	54.11 (5.79)	229.66 (8.46)
Goalaghat	29.55 (5.49)	15.7 (2.47)	40.17 (4.29)	48.3 (1.78)
Dhemaji	29.13 (5.42)	28.81 (4.53)	44.13 (4.72)	93.88 (3.46)
Dibrugarh	28.85 (5.36)	21.45 (3.38)	13.8 (1.48)	102.25 (3.77)
Others	236.89 (44.05)	399.5 (62.88)	517.48 (55.33)	2053.31 (75.67)
Assam	537.79 (100.00)	635.38 (100.00)	935.32 (100.00)	2713.65 (100)

Table 6: District wise CAGR of Area (ha) and production of cocoon and silk (MT) of Eri, Muga and Mulberry in Assam (2001-02 to 2015-16)

Districts	Area			Cocoon Production			Silk production		
	Eri	Muga	Mulberry	Eri	Muga	Mulberry	Eri	Muga	Mulberry
Karbi-Anglong	-0.14	4.34*	-1.21	3.05	35.88	6.55	2.74	34.49	2.62
N.C.Hills	-1.78	10.35*	3.04	6.93	45.46	24.8	6.44	45.04	19.52
Lakhimpur	-0.85	-2.72	4.92	13.79***	-2.41	9.60**	14.12***	-5.04*	9.08**
Sivasagar	-2.06	-3.3	-3.54	20.49	1.43	7.31*	20.96	1.91	3.84
Goalaghat	-4.85	0.1	-3.01	17.97***	4.57	8.77	17.83***	4.27	3.94
Dhemaji	6.24***	3.27*	1.02	9.73*	3.54*	13.14**	10.30*	3.09	12.90**
Dibrugarh	4.94**	0.87	1.25	16.28	12.74	6.60*	15.40***	12.73	4.37
Others	1.42	1.38	1.12	12.53***	17.92	6.04	14.53**	7.81	7.86
Assam	1.96	1.64	-0.43	14.5	3.06***	10.03**	14.77	2.59***	7.81**

***, ** & * indicates 1, 5 and 10 per cent level of significance

Conclusion:

Improvement in the sericulture activities in Assam and North Eastern States has been witnessed but at a very slow rate compared to traditional states like, Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu and West Bengal. North East India has contributed significantly to India's non-mulberry raw silk production as compared to mulberry. Growth of sericulture in Assam and NE India is relatively less in comparison to agricultural, industrial and service sectors. The area under sericulture in Assam has shown gradual increase in the past years but in recent years (2013-14 to 2015-16) it has declined due to shifting cultivation, gradual urbanization, fragmentation of land holdings, migration of rural youth to urban area etc. In case of mulberry, area has mainly decreased due to economically low demand of mulberry. In contrast, raw silk production of eri, muga and mulberry has increased in the state as well as majority of the districts of Assam during the period from 2001-02 to 2015-16. The reason for this increase in raw silk production of all the category of silk may be attributed to the factors like (i) adoption of new input technology, (ii) new hybrid silk worms of eri and muga introduced by Central Eri and Muga Research and Training Institute, Jorhat for high yield and quality of cocoons, (iii) advanced methods in reeling for raw silk production.

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